

RESEARCH AND PUBLICATION CENTER
UM Tagum College
Mabini St., Tagum City, Davao del Norte, Philippines

**1st International Research Conference for Graduate School and
2nd International Undergraduate Multidisciplinary Research Conference
June 22-24, 2022, via Online Platform**

Theme: Fostering Research Culture Amidst Global Crisis Through Practice and Innovation

**PREDICTORS OF WORK MOTIVATION AND RESILIENCE AMONG
NURSES IN LOCAL COVID CENTERS**

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ABSTRACT

This study is to determine the predictors of work resilience and motivation of nurses deployed in local quarantine and isolation centers in the selected municipalities and component city in Leyte for the year 2021. The respondents of the study were 123 nurses who have attained the casual, probationary and permanent status as of the conduct of the study regardless of their job tenure. Total enumeration sampling was employed. This descriptive-correlational predictive study utilized a standardized questionnaire divided into three parts formulated by Connor and Davidson wherein parametric measures and scoring stencils were employed. The study revealed that majority of the respondents were age-range 26-35 years old, along with genders 78.9% of them are females with 24.4% were male counterparts. Moreover, it was also noted that in terms of years rendered in the healthcare center, 65.9% have already dedicated their service of the profession for 1-5 years, while 3.3% have stayed to the profession for more than ten years. Furthermore, 37.4% have completed their Graduate Degree. Along with the level of intrinsic and extrinsic motivations, it revealed that nurses were intrinsically motivated are a moderate level having a mean of 3.12 (SD-0.53). Furthermore, it also insinuates that the resilience level of the nurses is generally on a high-level, with a mean score of 86.78 and lastly, resilience and motivation factors were significantly correlated at a 0.05 significance level. Between the resilience and their profile variable, it is deduced to have no significant correlation, but with motivation and their profile variable has significant correlation with age and educational variables as to the predictors identified in this study, resilience of nurses predicts their motivation along with challenge to the work aspect, enjoyment to the field and being outward to its stakeholders and colleague.

Keywords: work motivation, resilience, covid centers, descriptive – quantitative, Philippines